

Solar Profile Ratio of Building Forms: A Latitude-Dependent Geometric Index

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***Note 1:** This document is a working draft representing the current state of ongoing research. Certain figures & tables appear as placeholders pending final preparation. Comments are welcome. Please cite using the Zenodo DOI assigned at deposit.*

***Note 2:** This paper is the third in a series on the solar performance of building forms. In the present text, "Paper 1" refers to "A latitudinal study of insolation on geometric forms" (submitted to Solar Energy, May 2026); "Paper 2" refers to "Climatic compatibility of building forms as solar receivers across latitudes" (Zenodo preprint, May 2026). The present paper can be read independently; references to Papers 1 and 2 indicate shared datasets and methodology described therein.*

Abstract

This paper introduces the Solar Profile Ratio (SPR), a purely geometric index measuring the mean fraction of a building form's exposed surface projected toward the sun, averaged over the daylight hours of each month. Unlike irradiation-based metrics, SPR depends solely on building geometry and latitude, requiring no climate data or radiation database. It is computed for 92 form variants spanning seven generic solid types, identical to those of the companion papers on the m-index.

The paper is structured in two parts. Part A establishes the geometric law on a systematic latitude grid from 10°N to 80°N. The annual SPR (aSPR) correlates linearly with the base-to-surface ratio B/F at all latitudes, with a slope that decreases steadily from 10°N. All trendlines converge near B/F ≈ 0.2 -- the value of the cube -- which marks the boundary between two regimes: above it, flatter forms are sunnier at lower latitudes; below it, taller forms are sunnier at higher latitudes. The initial 10°-step results showed the slope turning negative above 60°N, prompting a follow-up computation at 1° resolution. This located the sign change precisely between 63°N and 64°N -- the latitude at which December daylight disappears from the annual average -- and identified the mechanism: the days-weighted averaging penalises wide flat forms more than tall narrow ones when winter months drop out.

Part B compares SPR with the m-index at nine locations (6.5°N–64.1°N). The Pearson correlation $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ exceeds 0.97 from Dakar (14.7°N) through Bologna (44.5°N), with Lagos slightly below at $r = 0.956$, declines at Aarhus, and collapses to -0.169 at Reykjavik, identifying a latitude threshold of geometric solar design at approximately 60°N. Above it, radiation climate dominates independently of form geometry.

36 The results establish the geometric foundation of the m-index framework and identify for the first time a
37 precise latitude boundary -- 63°--64°N -- above which geometric form optimisation loses its predictive
38 value for solar performance.

39 **Keywords:** *solar profile ratio, building geometry, B/F ratio, m-index, geometric solar index, latitude*
40 *threshold, passive solar design.*

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 The relationship between building form and solar radiation has been studied from multiple perspectives.
44 The concept of projecting a surface toward the sun is implicit in shading device calculations, but no
45 dimensionless whole-envelope index of this type, independent of radiation data and applied systematically
46 across form types and latitudes, appears in the existing literature. At the conceptual level, Olgyay [6]
47 established the principle that building form should respond to the specific climatic demands of its location.
48 More recent parametric studies -- Hachem et al. [4], Caruso et al. [2], Mohajeri et al. [5] -- have examined
49 specific geometric metrics in relation to irradiation, typically using surface-to-volume ratio or compactness
50 as descriptors. D'Amico and Pomponi [3] developed a scale-independent compactness measure and
51 demonstrated its utility for early-stage design.

52 A different approach was taken by the present author in a doctoral thesis [8] and subsequent works [9, 10]:
53 the base-to-surface ratio B/F was introduced as a dimensionless, scale-independent geometric parameter,
54 and its linear correlation with the form insolation index (m-index) was demonstrated across various convex
55 form types and locations. The companion Paper 1 [11] extends this to 92 form variants across 9 locations
56 from 6.5°N to 64.1°N using PVGIS v5.3 satellite data, confirming the relationship $m = u \cdot (B/F - 1) + 1$ with a
57 location-dependent slope coefficient u . Paper 2 [12] introduces the Climatic Compatibility Index (CC),
58 extending the m-index framework to seasonal resolution.

59 The linearity of the m-index with B/F is empirically well established. But its origin has remained an open
60 question: is it a consequence of the specific distribution of solar irradiance at each location, or does it have
61 a purely geometric root? If the latter, the same linear structure should be recoverable from solar geometry
62 alone, without any radiation database.

63 The present paper addresses this question by defining and computing the Solar Profile Ratio (SPR), a
64 radiation-free geometric index of solar exposure derived entirely from the angles between building face
65 normals and the solar ray direction. It is computed for 92 form variants at a systematic latitude grid (Part A)
66 and at the nine inherited locations of Paper 1 (Part B). The comparison of SPR with the m-index across
67 latitudes reveals the geometric foundation of the m-index and uncovers, along the way, an unexpected

68 inversion of the B/F gradient at high latitudes -- a result that prompted a secondary investigation described
69 in Section 4.4.

70 The study also uncovers an unexpected result: above approximately 64°N, the relationship between
71 building form geometry and solar exposure inverts -- a finding that emerges from the computation itself
72 rather than from any prior hypothesis.

73 **2. The Solar Profile Ratio (SPR)**

74 *2.1 Definition and Hierarchy*

75 The Solar Profile Ratio is defined as the fraction of a building form's total exposed surface area projected
76 toward the sun at a given instant compared to the total surface. It is defined at three temporal levels:

- 77 • Instantaneous Solar Profile Ratio (iSPR): the projected fraction at a single solar position.
- 78 • Monthly Solar Profile Ratio (mSPR): the average of iSPR over all daylight hours of a representative
79 day for each calendar month.
- 80 • Annual Solar Profile Ratio (aSPR): the days-weighted average of mSPR over all 12 months of the
81 year.

82 The hierarchy from iSPR to aSPR mirrors the averaging structure of the Form Insolation Index m in Paper 1
83 [11], enabling direct comparison at each temporal level. The annual average is weighted by the number of
84 days in each month, matching the computation of Paper 1 [11].

85 *2.2 Formula*

86 The Instantaneous Solar Profile Ratio is:

$$87 \quad \mathbf{iSPR} = \Sigma_f [A_f \times \cos \theta_f] / F$$

88 where the sum runs over all faces f of the building form, A_f is the area of face f , F is the total exposed
89 surface area, and θ_f is the angle of incidence on face f between the outward normal and the incoming solar
90 ray. Faces with $\theta > 90^\circ$ are pointing away from the sun and contribute zero. The result is dimensionless and
91 lies between 0 and 1.

92 *2.3 The Zenith Limiting Case: $iSPR = B/F$*

93 When the sun is at the zenith (solar altitude $\alpha = 90^\circ$), the solar ray is vertical. For the upright, non-
94 overhanging forms considered in this study, each surface element contributes only its horizontal projection
95 to the total projected area, and these sum to the base area B by construction. Therefore, at solar zenith:

$$96 \quad \mathbf{iSPR} = B / F$$

97 This identity connects the SPR index directly to the B/F parameter central to Papers 1 and 2. It
98 demonstrates that B/F is not an arbitrary geometric parameter but the exact solar exposure index at the
99 zenith limiting condition -- the geometric lower bound of the SPR, achieved when the sun is directly
100 overhead.

101 *2.4 Solar Geometry Model*

102 Solar declination, altitude and azimuth are computed from latitude and hour angle using the equations of
103 the NOAA Solar Calculator [7], which provides sufficient accuracy for the geometric purposes of this study.
104 Hour angle is sampled every 3.75° (approximately 15 minutes) within the daylight arc of a representative
105 day per month, defined by the sunrise hour angle. The PVGIS azimuth convention is used throughout (0° =
106 south, clockwise), ensuring consistency with the m-index data of Paper 1 [11]. The SPR calculation is strictly
107 independent of longitude, atmospheric conditions, and any radiation data.

109 **PART A -- The Geometric Law**

110 Systematic latitude grid (10°–80°N). Pure geometry, no radiation data.

111 **3. Study Setup -- Part A**

112 Part A computes the aSPR for all 92 form variants across a systematic latitude grid from 10°N to 80°N in
113 steps of 10°, giving eight latitudes in total. The upper bound of 80°N covers the inhabited Arctic fringe;
114 90°N is excluded as the polar geometry produces a sun that circles the horizon rather than rising and
115 setting in the conventional sense.

116 The 92 form variants span seven families: rectilinear boxes (B), pitched roofs (R), rectangular pyramids (P),
117 cones (K), cylinders (C), barrel vaults (V), and a hemisphere (H). Within each family, forms are parametrised
118 by height-to-width ratio (h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4), length-to-width ratio where applicable (l/w: 1, 2, 4), and
119 orientation where relevant (0°, 45°, 90°). Full codes and dimensions are listed in Table A (Appendix). These
120 are the same 92 variants used in Papers 1 and 2, enabling direct comparison across the series.

121 The computation is purely geometric: no irradiance data, atmospheric model, or climate database is used.
122 For each form and latitude, the iSPR is calculated at 15-minute hour-angle intervals throughout the daylight
123 arc of a representative day for each calendar month. The monthly values are averaged to give mSPR, and
124 the twelve monthly values are combined into the annual aSPR using a days-weighted average -- each
125 month weighted by its number of days -- matching the convention of Paper 1. All eight latitudes were
126 processed in a single computation run, ensuring identical parametrisation throughout.

127 **4. Results -- Part A**

128 **4.1 The Combined Trendline Chart**

129 The central visual result of Part A is the combined trendline chart (Figure 1), which plots the linear fits of
 130 aSPR vs B/F for all eight latitudes on a single graph. Three features stand out immediately:

- 131 • All eight trendlines are approximately linear across the B/F range of the 92 forms.
- 132 • The trendlines converge at a single point near B/F \approx 0.2, aSPR \approx 29–30 % -- the B/F value of the
 133 cube.
- 134 • Above the convergence point (B/F > 0.2), lower latitudes produce higher aSPR. Below it (B/F < 0.2),
 135 the order reverses.

136

137

138

139 *Figure 1: Combined aSPR vs B/F trendlines for all 8 latitudes (10°N–80°N). All lines converge near B/F \approx 0.2*
 140 *(the cube). The crossing of the trendlines below the convergence point indicates that taller forms are*
 141 *geometrically sunnier at higher latitudes than at lower ones.*

142 The linear fit parameters for each latitude are given in Table A. The R² values are high and stable between
 143 10°N and 50°N (0.91–0.93), then collapse sharply at 60°N (0.24). At 70°N and 80°N the slope is negative and

144 R² partially recovers (0.14–0.32). These observations prompted the follow-up investigation described in
 145 Section 4.4.

146 *Table A: aSPR vs B/F linear fit parameters by latitude (10°-step grid). Rows shaded yellow: slope near zero.*
 147 *Rows shaded red: slope negative*

Latitude	Slope	Intercept	R ²	Notes
10°N	37.759	21.718	0.9125	Near-equatorial; steepest slope
20°N	33.958	22.757	0.9151	
30°N	28.048	24.439	0.9235	
40°N	20.411	26.390	0.9318	
50°N	11.862	28.227	0.9099	
60°N	2.974	29.696	0.2439	R ² collapses; slope approaching zero
70°N	-2.432	25.332	0.1401	Slope negative -- gradient inverted
80°N	-3.631	20.838	0.3211	Near-polar; slope negative

148
 149 *4.2 Slope and Intercept as Functions of Latitude*

150 The slope of the aSPR vs B/F fit decreases steadily from approximately 38 at 10°N. It approaches zero
 151 around 60°N and is clearly negative at 70°N and 80°N. The behaviour of the slope is directly analogous to
 152 the u-coefficient of the m-index in Paper 1 [11] -- both measure the sensitivity of solar exposure to the B/F
 153 ratio of a form, one geometrically and one radiometrically. Their parallel decline with latitude indicates that
 154 the B/F structure of the m-index has a geometric foundation.

155 The intercept increases from approximately 21.7 % at 10°N to a maximum near 60°–67°N, then drops at
 156 higher latitudes. The intercept represents the aSPR of a theoretical infinitely tall vertical prism (B/F = 0): as
 157 the sun moves lower in the sky with increasing latitude, vertical surfaces receive proportionally more
 158 projected exposure, raising the baseline aSPR of tall forms. The drop at very high latitudes reflects the loss
 159 of entire winter months from the annual average, discussed further in Sec. 4.4.

160 An analytical fit of slope(ϕ) and intercept(ϕ) as functions of latitude yields a design formula for the 10°–
 161 60°N range:

162
$$\mathbf{aSPR(\phi, B/F) = [a \cdot \phi + b] \cdot B/F + [c \cdot \phi + d]}$$

163 The coefficients are determined by linear regression of the slope and intercept values from Table A across
 164 the 10°–60°N range, where both relationships are closely linear (R² = 0.997 and 0.991 respectively):

165
$$\mathbf{aSPR(\phi, B/F) = [-0.583 \cdot \phi + 43.6] \cdot B/F + [0.160 \cdot \phi + 20.1]}$$

166 where ϕ is latitude in degrees. Above 60°N the slope changes sign and the formula no longer applies; the
167 follow-up investigation in Section 4.4 addresses this range separately.

168 *4.3 The Convergence at the Cube: B/F ≈ 0.2*

169 The most immediately striking feature of Figure 1 is that all eight trendlines pass through approximately
170 the same point, near B/F ≈ 0.2 and aSPR ≈ 29–30 %. This B/F value is that of the cube -- the most compact
171 rectilinear form.

172 At B/F ≈ 0.2, all latitudes produce the same aSPR -- the cube is equally sunny everywhere. Above B/F = 0.2,
173 forms are dominated by near-horizontal surfaces and receive more solar exposure at lower latitudes, as
174 expected due to the high sun paths. Below B/F = 0.2, forms are dominated by vertical surfaces and the
175 gradient reverses: higher latitudes produce more projected exposure for these forms, because the lower
176 sun angles at high latitudes illuminate vertical walls more effectively. The cube balances these two
177 tendencies exactly, making it the form where latitude has the least influence on the direction of the solar
178 exposure gradient.

179 It is worth noting that the cube is also the most compact rectilinear form -- the one with minimum surface
180 for a given volume. The coincidence of geometric compactness and latitude-neutrality for solar exposure at
181 the same B/F value suggests a deeper connection between the two properties, which merits further
182 investigation.

183 *4.4 A Closer Look: The 60°–70°N Transition*

184 During the research, the unexpected slope behaviour above 60°N prompted a follow-up investigation. The
185 10°-step results showed the slope collapsing at 60°N and appearing negative at 70°N. This was not
186 anticipated. To understand what was happening -- and whether the inversion was genuine or a result of
187 the wide latitude spacing -- the computation was repeated across the 60°–70°N band in 1° steps, using all
188 92 forms and the same computation parameters as the main study.

189 The results are presented in Table B and Figure 2. The sign change is real and locates precisely between
190 63°N and 64°N. At 63°N the slope is still marginally positive (+0.303); at 64°N it is negative (–0.607). The
191 inversion deepens to a minimum around 67°N (–3.487), then partially stabilises. The 70°N value (–2.432)
192 matches the original Table A almost exactly, confirming that the two computations are consistent.

193 *Table B: aSPR vs B/F linear fit parameters at 1° resolution, 60°–70°N. Yellow: near-zero slope. Red: negative*
194 *slope. The sign change occurs between 63°N and 64°N.*

Latitude	Slope (ϕ)	Intercept (ϕ)	R ²	Notes
60°N	2.986	29.692	0.246	Slope positive; still above threshold
61°N	2.076	29.814	0.122	Declining

62°N	1.181	29.916	0.038	Near-zero
63°N	0.303	30.009	0.002	Near-zero; last positive value
64°N	-0.607	30.101	0.008	First negative -- December zeros out
65°N	-1.521	30.173	0.041	Steepest inversion
66°N	-2.481	30.200	0.088	
67°N	-3.487	30.170	0.134	
68°N	-2.625	27.760	0.122	November zeros out; intercept drops
69°N	-3.496	27.697	0.169	Consistent with 10°-step Table A
70°N	-2.432	25.332	0.140	

60-70°N aSPR vs B/F

Figure 2: aSPR vs B/F trendlines for latitudes 60°-70°N at 1° resolution (all 92 forms, days-weighted annual average). The lines fan from positive slope at 60°-63°N to negative slope at 64°-70°N. The sign change occurs between 63°N and 64°N, coinciding with the loss of December daylight from the annual average. The cluster of lines at the bottom (68°-70°N) reflects the additional loss of November above 68°N.

The mechanism behind the inversion is the disappearance of winter daylight. Above 64°N, December contributes zero to the annual average -- the sun no longer rises above the horizon on the representative day of that month. Since the annual aSPR is a days-weighted average, those 31 missing days pull the annual figure down. They do so asymmetrically: wide flat forms (high B/F) rely more heavily on summer sun, so losing a winter month costs them less in mSPR terms but more in day-count weight than it costs tall narrow forms, which collect radiation more evenly across the year. This imbalance tips the slope negative.

November follows the same pattern, disappearing from the computation at approximately 68°N. The drop in the intercept between 67°N and 68°N in Table B (from 30.17 to 27.76) marks this second threshold precisely.

210 These thresholds are not gradual -- they occur within a single degree of latitude, at the point where an
 211 entire calendar month drops out of the annual average.

212
 213 **PART B -- Validation and Climate Comparison**

214 Nine inherited locations (6.5°–64.1°N). Comparison of SPR with m-index from
 215 Paper 1.
 216

217 **5. Study Setup -- Part B**

218 Part B computes the SPR for all 92 form variants at the nine locations inherited from Paper 1 [11], spanning
 219 6.5°N (Lagos) to 64.1°N (Reykjavik). These locations were selected for Paper 1 [11] based on geographic
 220 spread across latitudes; their Köppen classifications are noted for reference. The uneven latitude sampling
 221 is a methodological constraint shared across the paper series. The locations are listed in Table 2 together
 222 with the Pearson correlation $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ values from Section 6.2.

223 *Table C: Study locations for Part B, inherited from Paper 1 [11], with correlation $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ values.*

Location	Code	Lat.	Köppen	Ann. T (°C)	$r(\text{SPR}, m)$	Comments
Lagos	LAG	6.5°N	Aw	26.7	0.956	Tropical baseline
Dakar	DAK	14.7°N	BSh	24.2	0.972	Transitional
Riyadh	RIY	24.7°N	BWh	26.9	0.979	Hot desert
Alexandria	ALE	31.2°N	BWh	21.2	0.985	Mediterranean arid
Athens	ATH	38.0°N	Csa	18.4	0.993	Mediterranean
Bologna	BOL	44.5°N	Cfa	14.0	0.980	Highest discrimination
London	LON	51.5°N	Cfb	11.1	0.944	Onset of decoupling
Aarhus	AAR	56.2°N	Cfb	9.4	0.824	Strong decoupling
Reykjavik	REY	64.1°N	Cfc	4.0	-0.169	Complete collapse

Figure 3: Map showing the 9 study locations.

Because SPR is longitude-independent, SPR values for each location are universal for that latitude band. Both monthly and annual SPR were computed for all 92 form variants at each location, using the same solar geometry model as Part A.

Figure 4: aSPR for all 92 forms at 9 locations, ordered by B/F. Below B/F ≈ 0.2, lower-latitude locations (LAG, DAK, RIY) produce lower aSPR than higher-latitude ones -- the gradient is inverted. Above B/F ≈ 0.2, lower latitudes are sunnier, as expected. Reykjavik (REY, dotted) shows no consistent relationship with the other locations across the full B/F range, reflecting the collapse of geometric ordering above 60°N."

6. Results -- Part B

6.1 Monthly SPR Profiles

The monthly Solar Profile Ratio (mSPR) follows characteristic seasonal patterns that depend on the B/F ratio of the form and the latitude of the location. Three signatures are observed:

High B/F forms (wide, flat: pyramids, cones at low h/w, shallow pitched roofs). mSPR peaks in summer and reaches a minimum in winter. Near-horizontal surfaces receive maximum projected solar exposure when the sun is high. The seasonal amplitude increases with latitude.

Low B/F forms (tall, narrow: elongated boxes at high h/w, steep pitched roofs). mSPR peaks in winter and is lower in summer. Vertical surfaces project more effectively toward the low winter sun. The seasonal amplitude of this inversion grows with latitude, consistent with the Part A finding that the latitude gradient of aSPR reverses at low B/F.

Intermediate forms. mSPR varies seasonally with intermediate amplitude, tracking neither extreme.

248 The scatter visible in Figure 4 around the general B/F trend reveals the influence of secondary geometric
 249 factors. Within each B/F group, forms with the same ratio but different orientations or elongation (l/w)
 250 produce noticeably different aSPR values -- visible as spikes in the figure. The most pronounced deviations
 251 occur in elongated boxes at $\alpha=90^\circ$ (large south-facing walls producing higher-than-expected aSPR at low
 252 B/F) and in shallow pitched roofs and pyramids at high B/F (where slope angle introduces a secondary
 253 effect). These secondary factors account for the residual variance not captured by B/F alone, consistent
 254 with the R^2 values of 0.91--0.93 observed in Part A. B/F therefore describes the first-order pattern of solar
 255 exposure across form types; orientation and elongation modulate it at a secondary level.

256 *6.2 Pearson $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ by Latitude -- The Threshold*

257 The Pearson correlation r between the SPR pattern and the m -index pattern across all 92 forms measures how
 258 well pure geometry predicts radiation-based performance at each location:

- 259 • $r > 0.97$ for locations from Dakar (14.7°N) through Bologna (44.5°N), with Lagos slightly below at $r =$
 260 0.956. Across this range -- spanning tropical, desert, Mediterranean, and humid subtropical climates
 261 -- climate type has negligible effect on the form ranking. Geometry governs.
- 262 • $r = 0.944$ at London. This is the first measurable decline, beginning of decoupling.
- 263 • $r = 0.824$ at Aarhus (56.2°N). Substantial decline. Individual form rankings begin to deviate from the
 264 geometric prediction.
- 265 • $r = -0.169$ at Reykjavik (64.1°N). Complete collapse. Here, the SPR pattern and m -index pattern are
 266 completely uncorrelated -- knowing a form's geometric solar exposure tells you nothing about its
 267 radiation-based m -index at this latitude.

268
 269 *Figure 5: Pearson $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ as a function of latitude for all 9 locations. Near-constant above 0.97 from 6°N to
 270 44°N; decline begins after 44°N; collapse to near-zero at 64°N. Latitude threshold of geometric solar design
 271 identified at approximately 60°N.*

272 The pattern identifies a latitude threshold of geometric solar design at approximately 60°N. Below this
 273 threshold, form geometry governs the pattern of solar radiation received by the envelope; climate merely
 274 scales the absolute values without altering the relative ranking of forms. Above it, radiation climate

275 reorganises the form hierarchy independently of geometry. The connection between Part A and Part B is
276 direct: the R^2 collapse at 60°N in Part A and the r collapse at Reykjavik in Part B are two views of the same
277 phenomenon. Both are further explained by the K_d effect discussed in Section 7.8.

278 **7. Discussion**

279 *7.1 The Geometric Foundation of the m-index*

280 The central finding of this paper is that the linear relationship between B/F and annual solar exposure --
281 first established empirically for the m-index [8, 11] -- is reproduced by the purely geometric SPR. This
282 confirms that the B/F linearity of the m-index is not a radiation phenomenon but a geometric one, arising
283 from the mathematical structure of solar projection geometry applied to convex forms. The agreement
284 holds across all 92 forms at locations below 56°N ; deviations at higher latitudes are addressed in Sections
285 6.2 and 7.8.

286 The u-coefficient of the m-index (the slope of the linear m vs B/F relationship established in Paper 1 [11])
287 and the slope of aSPR vs B/F are the same physical quantity evaluated with and without radiation
288 weighting. Their close correspondence across the latitude range where $r(\text{SPR}, m) > 0.97$ confirms that
289 radiation weighting does not alter the form hierarchy in this range -- it only scales the absolute values.

290 *7.2 $R^2(\phi)$ and $r(\phi)$ as Complementary Diagnostics*

291 $R^2(\phi)$ from Part A measures internal consistency: how well the geometric SPR is predicted by B/F alone
292 within the form set. Correlation $r(\phi)$ from Part B measures external validity: how well the geometric SPR
293 predicts the radiation-based m-index. Both degrade in the same latitude range -- above approximately
294 56°N -- corroborating the threshold from two independent methodological directions. It should be noted
295 that the r decline above 56°N reflects both geometric decoupling and the increasing dominance of diffuse
296 radiation at high latitudes -- two effects that are not separable within the present dataset and are
297 discussed further in Section 7.8.

298 *7.3 The SPR/m Ratio as a Climate Efficiency Indicator*

299 Where SPR/m is approximately constant across forms at a given location (as it is below $\sim 56^\circ\text{N}$), the
300 atmosphere treats all forms approximately equally -- scaling the geometric exposure by a common factor
301 without altering the form hierarchy. This 'uniform scaling' regime is what makes B/F-based form
302 optimisation effective below the threshold. Above it, diffuse radiation -- isotropic and orientation-neutral --
303 dominates, breaking the uniform scaling and producing a form hierarchy that diverges from the geometric
304 prediction.

305 *7.4 The $i\text{SPR} = B/F$ Identity as Theoretical Anchor*

306 The identity $iSPR = B/F$ at the solar zenith connects Papers 1 & 2 to the present one through their shared
307 geometric parameter. The m-index formula $m = u \cdot (B/F - 1) + 1$ from Paper 1 [11] can now be understood
308 geometrically: at $u = 1$ (the theoretical maximum, approached at very low latitudes), the formula reduces
309 to $m = B/F$, reproducing the zenith limiting case. The u-coefficient is the radiation-weighted analogue of the
310 geometric slope of aSPR vs B/F. This grounding suggests that the linear form of the m-index formula is not
311 an approximation but a consequence of the geometry of convex forms under solar projection.

312 *7.5 The Cube as Geometric Pivot*

313 The convergence of all latitude trendlines near $B/F \approx 0.2$ -- the cube -- identifies the cube as the form where
314 the direction of the latitude gradient changes sign. It is not that the cube has the same aSPR at all latitudes
315 -- its aSPR decreases with latitude like every other form -- but that it sits at the boundary between the two
316 regimes. Flatter forms are sunnier at lower latitudes; taller forms are sunnier at higher latitudes; the cube
317 is neither.

318 This coincides with the cube's recognised status as the most compact rectilinear form -- the one with
319 minimum surface for a given volume. Whether this coincidence reflects a deeper geometric principle is an
320 open question.

321 *7.6 Design Implications*

322 Below approximately $60^\circ N$, the B/F ratio reliably predicts relative solar performance across form types.
323 Form optimisation based on B/F is valid and transferable throughout all locations below $60^\circ N$, which
324 includes the vast majority of the world's building stock. Above the threshold, the B/F gradient not only
325 weakens but inverts: a form optimised for maximum solar reception at mid-latitudes becomes
326 geometrically the worst performer above $64^\circ N$. At these latitudes, form optimisation requires direct
327 radiation data rather than geometric proxies.

328 *7.7 The 63° – $64^\circ N$ Threshold: A Sharp Geometric Boundary*

329 The follow-up probe reveals that the transition from positive to negative slope is not a gradual process but
330 a step change occurring within a single degree of latitude. Above $64^\circ N$, December drops out of the annual
331 average entirely. This removes 31 days of data from every form's annual figure simultaneously -- but not
332 symmetrically. Wide flat forms lose relatively more, because their winter mSPR was already low and the
333 lost days are winter days. Tall narrow forms lose less, because their mSPR is more stable across seasons.
334 The result is an inversion of the competitive ranking between flat and tall forms that is sudden, not gradual.
335 November follows at approximately $68^\circ N$, marking a second step. Between $64^\circ N$ and $67^\circ N$, December is
336 gone but November is not; above $68^\circ N$, both are gone. Each threshold produces a visible discontinuity in
337 the intercept of the aSPR vs B/F fit, visible in Table B as the drop between $67^\circ N$ and $68^\circ N$.

338 These are not climatic boundaries -- they are geometric ones, imposed by the horizon condition and the
339 days-weighted averaging. They are sharp, predictable, and computable from solar geometry alone.

340 *7.8 Limitations*

- 341 • Hour-angle sampling at 15-minute intervals introduces a small discretisation error, estimated below
342 1 % of the daily mSPR.
- 343 • Curved surfaces are approximated by discrete flat facets (8 sectors for cones and cylinders, 4 zones
344 × 8 azimuths for the hemisphere), introducing a small systematic error for highly curved forms.
- 345 • A single representative day per month is used; accuracy is within the natural variability of solar
346 geometry within the month.
- 347 • The latitude sampling in Part B is uneven and inherited from Paper 1 [11]. The gap between Aarhus
348 (56.2°N) and Reykjavik (64.1°N) means the precise location of the Part B radiation threshold cannot
349 be determined from this dataset.
- 350 • The comparison between SPR and the m-index in Part B conflates two distinct causes of decoupling
351 at high latitudes. SPR tracks only the geometric projection of direct beam radiation; the m-index,
352 derived from PVGIS data, includes both direct and diffuse components. At high latitudes the diffuse
353 fraction K_d increases substantially -- at Reykjavik diffuse radiation accounts for the majority of
354 annual global irradiation. Since diffuse radiation is approximately isotropic, it illuminates all surfaces
355 nearly equally regardless of orientation or B/F, pushing the m-index toward a uniform value across
356 form types and decoupling it from the geometric hierarchy captured by SPR. The r collapse at
357 Reykjavik is therefore a joint effect of geometric decoupling -- identified and quantified in this paper
358 -- and K_d -driven diffuse dominance, which cannot be separated from this dataset. Isolating the two
359 contributions would require computing the m-index from direct radiation only, or comparing SPR
360 against a beam-fraction-weighted version of the m-index. This remains a direction for future work.

361 **8. Conclusions**

362 This paper introduced the Solar Profile Ratio (SPR) and computed it for 92 building form variants across a
363 systematic latitude grid (Part A) and nine inherited locations (Part B). The following conclusions are drawn:

- 364 • SPR is linearly correlated with B/F across all latitudes from 10°N to 80°N, confirming that the
365 empirical B/F linearity of the m-index has a geometric origin in solar projection geometry.
- 366 • The slope of aSPR vs B/F decreases from approximately 38 at 10°N, approaches zero around 60°N,
367 and becomes negative above 64°N. A follow-up investigation at 1° resolution located the sign
368 change precisely between 63°N and 64°N -- the latitude at which December daylight disappears

369 from the computation. The inversion deepens to a minimum around 67°N, then a second step
370 occurs at 68°N when November also disappears (visible as the intercept drop in Table B between
371 67°N and 68°N).

- 372 • All latitude trendlines converge near $B/F \approx 0.2$, the value of the cube. The cube is the geometric
373 pivot: the form at which the direction of the latitude gradient changes sign. Below $B/F = 0.2$, taller
374 forms are geometrically sunnier at higher latitudes; above it, flatter forms are sunnier at lower
375 latitudes.
- 376 • The R^2 of the aSPR vs B/F fit is stable at 0.91–0.93 between 10°N and 50°N, collapses at 60°N (0.24),
377 and partially recovers at 70°–80°N as the negative gradient re-establishes itself.
- 378 • The Pearson correlation $r(\text{SPR}, m)$ exceeds 0.97 for the locations from Dakar (14.7°N) through
379 Bologna, with Lagos slightly below at $r = 0.956$, declines to 0.824 at Aarhus (56.2°N), and collapses
380 to -0.169 at Reykjavik (64.1°N), identifying a latitude threshold of geometric solar design at
381 approximately 60°N.
- 382 • Below the threshold, SPR and m are structurally equivalent: radiation climate scales the geometric
383 exposure without altering the relative form ranking. Above it, radiation climate decouples from
384 form geometry and the form hierarchy reorganises independently of B/F .
- 385 • The $i\text{SPR} = B/F$ identity at the solar zenith connects the SPR framework to the m -index of Paper 1
386 [11] and the CC index of Paper 2 [12] through their shared geometric parameter B/F . Together, the
387 three indices constitute a three-layer analytical framework: SPR as the pure geometric baseline, m
388 as its climate-modulated counterpart, and CC as the measure of seasonal timing.
- 389 • The precise location of the Part B radiation threshold within the 56°–64°N band and the exact
390 crossover B/F value of the cube convergence remain open for future work requiring denser location
391 sampling.

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418

419 **Appendix: Form List**

420 *Table D: All 92 building form variants with codes and descriptions.*

code	data	image
B1	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=1 or=0	
B2	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=1 or= 45	
B3	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=2 or=0	
B4	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=2 or=45	
B5	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=2 or=90	
B6	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=4 or=0	
B7	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=4 or=45	
B8	Box h/w=0.25 l/w=4 or=90	
B9	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=1 or=0	
B10	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=1 or=45	
B11	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=2 or=0	
B12	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=2 or=45	
B13	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=2 or=90	
B14	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=4 or=0	
B15	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=4 or=45	
B16	Box h/w=0.5 l/w=4 or=90	
B17	Box h/w=1 l/w=1 or=0	
B18	Box h/w=1 l/w=1 or=45	
B19	Box h/w=1 l/w=2 or=0	
B20	Box h/w=1 l/w=2 or=45	
B21	Box h/w=1 l/w=2 or=90	
B22	Box h/w=1 l/w=4 or=0	
B23	Box h/w=1 l/w=4 or=45	
B24	Box h/w=1 l/w=4 or=90	

B25	Box h/w=2 l/w=1 or=0	
B26	Box h/w=2 l/w=1 or=45	
B27	Box h/w=2 l/w=2 or=0	
B28	Box h/w=2 l/w=2 or=45	
B29	Box h/w=2 l/w=2 or=90	
B30	Box h/w=2 l/w=4 or=0	
B31	Box h/w=2 l/w=4 or=45	
B32	Box h/w=2 l/w=4 or=90	
B33	Box h/w=4 l/w=1 or=0	
B34	Box h/w=4 l/w=1 or=45	
B35	Box h/w=4 l/w=2 or=0	
B36	Box h/w=4 l/w=2 or=45	
B37	Box h/w=4 l/w=2 or=90	
B38	Box h/w=4 l/w=4 or=0	

B39	Box h/w=4 l/w=4 or=45	
B40	Box h/w=4 l/w=4 or=90	
R1	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=0.25 or=0	
R2	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=0.25 or=90	
R3	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=1 or=0	
R4	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=1 or=90	
R5	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=4 or=0	
R6	Pitched h/w=0.25 l/w=4 or=90	
R7	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=0.25 or=0	
R8	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=0.25 or=90	
R9	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=1 or=0	
R10	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=1 or=90	
R11	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=4 or=0	
R12	Pitched h/w=0.5 l/w=4 or=90	
R13	Pitched h/w=1 l/w=0.25 or=0	
R14	Pitched h/w=1 l/w=0.25 or=90	
R15	Pitched h/w=1 l/w=1 or=0	
R16	Pitched h/w=1 l/w=1 or=90	
R17	Pitched h/w=1 l/w=4 or=0	

R18	Pitched $h/w=1$ $l/w=4$ or $=90$	
R19	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=0.25$ or $=0$	
R20	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=0.25$ or $=90$	
R21	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=1$ or $=0$	
R22	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=1$ or $=90$	
R23	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=4$ or $=0$	
R24	Pitched $h/w=2$ $l/w=4$ or $=90$	
R25	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=0.25$ or $=0$	
R26	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=0.25$ or $=90$	
R27	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=1$ or $=0$	
R28	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=1$ or $=90$	
R29	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=4$ or $=0$	

R30	Pitched $h/w=4$ $l/w=4$ or $=90$	
P1	Pyramid $h/w=0.25$	
P2	Pyramid $h/w=0.5$	
P3	Pyramid $h/w=1$	
P4	Pyramid $h/w=2$	
P5	Pyramid $h/w=4$	
K1	Cone $h/w=0.25$	
K2	Cone $h/w=0.5$	
K3	Cone $h/w=1$	
K4	Cone $h/w=2$	
K5	Cone $h/w=4$	
C1	Cylinder $h/w=0.25$	
C2	Cylinder $h/w=0.5$	
C3	Cylinder $h/w=1$	
C4	Cylinder $h/w=2$	
C5	Cylinder $h/w=4$	
V1	Vault $l/w=1$ or $=0$	
V2	Vault $l/w=1$ or $=90$	

V3 Vault $l/w=2$ or $=0$

V4 Vault $l/w=2$ or $=90$

V5 Vault $l/w=4$ or $=0$

V6 Vault $l/w=4$ or $=90$

H1 Hemisphere

